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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D7.3 (D28):

Report from SONNET on Tour workshops

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2	Dutch Research Institute for Transitions	DRIFT	NL	
3	University of Sussex, with its Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU)	UoS	UK	
4	Grenoble Ecole de Management	GEM	FR	
5	Akademia Leona Kozminkiego	ALK	PL	
6	Zuercher Hochschule for Applied Research	ZHAW	CH	
7	ICLEI European Secretariat	ICLEI	DE	
8	City of Mannheim	MANN	GER	
9	City of Antwerp	ANTW	BE	
10	City of Bristol	BRIS	UK	
11	City of Grenoble	GREN	FR	
12	City of Warsaw	WARS	PL	
13	City of Basel (Associated Partner)	BASE	CH	

Executive Summary

D7.3 reports on the two SONNET on Tour workshops, including their agendas and minutes, featuring participants' reflections and main conclusions. The report has been designed in an easy to read format, including pictures, quotes and other materials that were used in the workshop.

Originally the workshops were planned as in-person workshops with SIE initiatives and local governments representatives as key audience. Whereas these audiences were reached in both workshops, both in diversity and numbers, the character of the workshops had to be adapted to continuing COVID restrictions. The workshops delivered the desired outcomes with the necessary adaptations also through hybrid and online formats.

Key outcomes of the workshops were a set of potential ideas for new City Labs, developed by participants in each workshop based on a Social Innovation in Energy (SIE) canvas; communication material was produced in shape of a video about a community centre that participated in the SONNET City Lab in Bristol, showcasing the City Lab themes and approaches; and in Warsaw the workshop ended with an unanimous expression of interest between local government representatives and SIE initiatives to meet on a regular basis to exchange and support each other.

Table of Contents

1	Setting the scene.....	3
2	Zoom in on SONNET on Tour in Bristol	4
2.1	SONNET on Tour in Bristol: agenda.....	4
2.2	SONNET on Tour in Bristol: participants.....	7
2.3	SONNET on Tour in Bristol: meeting minutes	9
2.4	SONNET on Tour in Bristol: outputs.....	13
3	Zoom in on SONNET on Tour in Warsaw	14
3.1	SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: agenda	14
3.2	SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: participants	17
3.3	SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: minutes.....	19
3.4	SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: outputs.....	25
4	Appendix 1: City Lab canvases from Bristol	26
5	Appendix 2: City Lab canvases from Warsaw	32
6	Appendix 2: EC summary requirements.....	37

Figures

Figure 1: Countries represented among SONNET on Tour in Bristol participants, considering only actual attendees (and not also those who registered and did not attend).....	7
Figure 2: Screenshot of the pre-recorded site visit video.....	9
Figure 3: Impression from first round of the SIE canvas exercise (Bristol).....	11
Figure 4: European countries represented in day one by event registrations	17
Figure 5: Screenshots from OpenLap (Tartu, Estonia) presentation.....	20
Figure 6: Screenshot from Z-Klaster (Poland) presentation.....	21
Figure 7: Impression from first round of the SIE canvas exercise (Warsaw).....	21
Figure 8: Screenshots from presentation of the UrbanLab (Gdynia, Poland).....	23
Figure 9: Screenshot from SONNET City Lab in Warsaw presentation	23

Tables

Table 1: Agenda of day 1, Tuesday, 16 November 2021, roundtable.....	4
Table 2: Agenda of day 2, Wednesday, 17 November 2021, workshop.....	5
Table 3: Agenda of day 1, Thursday, 27 January 2022, open to all.....	14
Table 4: Agenda of day 2, Friday, 28 January 2022, by-invitation workshop.....	15

1 SETTING THE SCENE

The two 'SONNET on Tour' workshops were planned as regional (supra-national), 1.5-day training workshops with approx. 30 participants, both being hosted by a SONNET city. The city of Warsaw was foreseen for the region of Eastern, Central and Southern Europe, whereas the city of Bristol was intended to cover Northern and Western Europe. This setup was generally implemented. However, inviting participants from across Europe to join in-person was not possible under COVID circumstances. The restrictions led to considering a more sub-national understanding of region and the closer ties to SIE actors from the same country as well as neighbouring countries. This consideration was also strengthened by the two cities own experiences made throughout the City Lab and the interest in sharing and exchanging about those – if possible in an in-person setting. In Bristol this had led to considering UK examples of so-called Community Municipal Bonds, an approach that had been informed by other UK municipalities and was seen as rather specific for that context. It was however mirrored with European experience by including insights on crowdlending approaches in Spain and Portugal (see ch.2). For Warsaw, in a similar line, the national legislative context was specific for the City Lab as a local experimentation SIE type, which created the strong interest to exchange with similar cases in the country. As in the Bristol case, this focus was enriched with a wider European perspective by including insights from Estonia and Bulgaria.

Both workshops at last took place in phases of high uncertainty with regard to COVID. The workshop in Bristol was held in a hybrid format, with participants from the UK and specifically the Bristol region participating in person and all other participants, including co-moderation, participating online (cf. ch. 2.2). The Warsaw workshop was split into an all-online part and an all-in-person part; eventually this had to be shifted into a completely all-online format. Both workshops involved the local, as well as other regional SIE initiatives and managed to invite specifically local government representatives to participate. These came for the already mentioned practical reasons mostly from the host country.

To share the methods and results from SONNET's work not only through presentations and discussion, but also have participants applying the ideas themselves, a so-called "SIE canvas" was developed. This approach built on the method of the business model canvas and translated SONNET City Lab-specific aspects into a similar format. The SIE canvas was tested and co-developed with the project consortium through two workshops and feedback loops before applying it in the SONNET on tour workshops. In the workshops, participants were encouraged to apply the learnings shared through a simplified and easy-to-grasp canvas to their own local context and to develop a first City Lab prototype (a "micro lab") for their city or neighbourhood (see appendices 1 and 2 for the outcomes).

2 ZOOM IN ON SONNET ON TOUR IN BRISTOL

2.1 SONNET on Tour in Bristol: agenda

On 16–17 November 2021, the [SONNET project](#) held a targeted expert workshop, exploring the potential, success stories, and challenges of innovative financing mechanisms like Community Municipal Bonds (CMBs), with a focus on how to use these green bonds to advance local energy transitions. The event title was “Financing local energy transitions: Expert roundtable workshop on supporting energy transitions through green bonds”.

Those with experience in this topic, and/or who are keen to push forward such efforts in their own communities were invited to join and engage in a site visit, discussions and hands-on exercises. This invitation was extended to Bristol’s network of fellow U.K. local councils, all who had previously participated in SONNET online seminars, ICLEI Europe’s U.K. Member Cities, and to the Bristol Energy Network’s extended network of community energy leaders.

The workshop was held at the [Knowle West Media Centre](#) in Bristol (UK), with a site visit to Filwood Community Centre, which is, through SONNET, exploring [making use of CMBs to invest in energy improvements](#). Travel reimbursement was made available for participants, and the workshop could also be joined online (via Zoom) for those unable to travel to Bristol.

Table 1: Agenda of day 1, Tuesday, 16 November 2021, roundtable

TIME (GMT)	PROGRAMME
9:00 – 9:45	Introduction and tour of Filwood Community Centre led by Matt Jones, Bristol City Council (<i>for in-person participants</i>)
9:45 – 10:05	Welcome and pre-recorded tour of Filwood Community Centre (watch on YouTube here) shown over Zoom to online participants* <i>*during this time, in-person participants walk the 8 minutes from Filwood to the event venue at Knowle West Media Centre</i>
10:05 – 11:00	Session 1: THE BASICS Local energy transition in Bristol: status quo, challenges and solutions & the potential of a Community Municipal Bond (CMB), with conversation leaders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Richard Lowe, Bristol City Council - Dave Tudgey, Bristol Energy Network - Q&A and discussion moderated by Adrienne Kotler, ICLEI Europe

11:00 – 12:30 (open ended)	<p>Session 2: SUCCESS FACTORS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Series of ‘pitches’ describing innovative financing success stories, followed by a moderated panel discussion amongst the conversation leaders who have ‘pitched’ their work: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Joseph Holmes, West-Berkshire Municipality - Karl Harder, Abundance Investment - Ryan Jude, Green Finance Institute - Manuel Nina, GOPARITY impact investing - Moderation (including moderating a discussion with participants) by Niklas Mischkowski, ICLEI Europe - Closing by Lorna Humphreys, Bristol City Council
13:00 – 13:45	Optional: lunch catered at the Knowle West Media Centre
13:45 – 15:45	Optional: Bristol’s SONNET City Lab closing event: listen in on this discussion with community building managers who have been engaged in the SONNET project in Bristol, to discuss the future of how Bristol will help fund energy efficiency improvements in community buildings.

Table 2: Agenda of day 2, Wednesday, 17 November 2021, workshop

TIME (GMT)	PROGRAMME
9:00 – 9:30	<p>Introduction and welcome</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Niklas Mischkowski introduces today’s workshop - Participants write down (1) <i>energy transition challenges</i>, and (2) <i>visions for a change they want to see to strengthen local energy transition</i> (on post-it notes or using MIRO for online participants)
9:30 – 10:15	<p>Session 3: EXPERIENCES</p> <p>Discussion on how to use a City Lab approach to implement CMB and related innovative financing mechanisms. Discussion touched on defining a City Lab, examining how Bristol has used a City Lab, and how it helped shape local energy transition, with conversation leaders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sabine Hielscher, University of Sussex - Caroline Bird, Bristol Energy Network - Q&A and discussion moderated by Niklas Mischkowski, ICLEI Europe

<p>10:15 – 11:15</p>	<p>Session 4: THE MICRO LAB – design your own local experiment for energy transition</p> <p>All participants were part of this micro lab, which was designed and facilitated by Niklas Mischkowski with Adrienne Kotler.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. During the previous session, Adrienne Kotler had clustered participants' identified challenges and visions into nine topics II. At the beginning of the micro lab, SONNET on Tour participants voted on which topics they wished to explore further. Based on the three most popular choices, three breakout groups were formed. III. Groups talked through their selected topics and identified potential 'local experiments' that could be applied (using a City Lab approach) to forge their desired vision for change. IV. Both with their fellow breakout group members and individually, participants used a pre-prepared canvas template to identify factors such as their vision, proposed innovation to test, key actors to engage, communication needs, etc. V. Group members presented their ideas to each other, provided feedback, and adjusted canvases accordingly. VI. All groups returned to the plenary to present their templates to one another.
<p>11:25 – 12:15</p>	<p>Session 5: PROMOTE AND DEBATE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A closing panel discussion explored motivations, needs and barriers related to financing local energy transitions, with conversation leaders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Richard Lowe, Bristol City Council - Rachel Moffat, Bristol Energy Network - Karl Harder, Abundance Investment - Moderation (including moderating a discussion with participants) by Matt Jones, Bristol City Council - Closing by Matt Jones and Niklas Mischkowski, Bristol City Council <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants share something they are called to do as a result of these past two days of discussion.

2.2 SONNET on Tour in Bristol: participants

SONNET successfully met our target in Bristol of engaging approximately 30 participants from Northern & Western Europe, with a focus on the region around Bristol. This event also had impressive ‘follow-through’ among registrants, with 35 participants having registered, and 31 ultimately attending.

Of the 31 participants who attended, 18 (58%) joined the hybrid event online, and 13 (42%) joined in-person in Bristol. Participants represented seven countries in Northern and Western Europe (see Figure 1). Furthermore, five different local councils in the U.K. were present for the event, indicating that there was a strong appetite for Bristol’s neighbours to learn from their experience.

Figure 1: Countries represented among SONNET on Tour in Bristol participants, considering only actual attendees (and not also those who registered and did not attend).

There was less attendance on the second day of the event compared to the first. This was, in part, because Day 1 included a short “City Lab Closing Event” in the afternoon for building managers in Bristol, who thus attended the morning session on Day 1 as well. In addition, one online participant expressed that they found it frustrating not to be present for the in-person discussions, and thus were turned off from joining on Day 2.

Following the conclusion of the event, all those who registered were asked to fill in an online evaluation form, which was catered to different audiences such that the questions that appeared differed for those who did and did not attend, and for those who attended online versus in-person.

This evaluation form was highly informative, and demonstrated that the event was a success. Participants were asked to rate their satisfaction with various components of the event on a Likert scale (1= Very Poor; 2= Poor; 3= Okay; 4= Good; 5= Excellent). No one responded below a “3” on any component of the event. Furthermore, participants *on average* rated their satisfaction as follows:

- Satisfaction with the event as a whole: average **4.25**
- Satisfaction with the content of the sessions: average **4.25**
- Satisfaction with the speakers: **4.25**
- Satisfaction with interactivity and discussions: average **4**
- Satisfaction with the moderators: average **4**

Participants also had the opportunity to share reflections openly. This led to the following submissions:

- “The event was interesting and valuable – well done!”
- “I look forward to following-up on connections made.”
- “My highlight was hearing about the success of the West Berkshire Council community bond initiative.”
- “Thank you for organising and for giving the possibility for either online and in-person participation.”
- **“I will be starting conversations in my own Council about the possibility of launching community municipal bonds to support the local energy transition in our area.”**

2.3 SONNET on Tour in Bristol: meeting minutes

Day 1

The event began with a **guided tour** to the Filwood Community Centre, which was offered live to in-person participants, while a [pre-recorded version](#) was played for those who joined online. This set the scene for the event, providing participants with a clearer picture of *who* in Bristol is looking to use a CMB, and *how* such a mechanism could concretely support energy transition locally.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the pre-recorded site visit video

All participants (online and in-person) then convened at Knowle West Media Centre (KWMC) for the workshop sessions. To bring all participants on the same page, everyone was welcomed at the KWMC by Lorna Huphreys (BCC), who briefly introduced BCC’s engagement within the SONNET project as part of the city’s overall climate policy efforts. After this introduction, ICLEI took over moderation, introducing the participants, and providing an overview of the agenda for the day.

In “**Session 1: THE BASICS – energy transition in Bristol**”, Richard Lowe, Investment Manager for Energy Services of BCC, and David Tudgey, Project Development Manager at Bristol Energy Network (BEN), gave a more in-depth introduction to the city’s energy transition agenda and challenges faced with regard to the financing of measures.

An important aspect covered was BCC’s “Social Value Policy” which commits the city council to make decisions based on a more holistic definition of ‘value for money’. All Social Value commitments are embedded in contracts and externally monitored. It is against this background that CMB has been explored as a participatory finance model, and why it was chosen to be tested within the SONNET project.

David Tudgey emphasised the importance and potential stemming from the fact that CMBs are community-centred. They work only where communities are interested in becoming shareholders of energy infrastructure. Finally, he presented just how important it is that BEN acts as an intermediary partner between the council and local residents.

The second session focused on “**Debating SUCCESS FACTORS**”, based on the experience of four speakers:

1. Joseph Holmes, [West-Berkshire municipality](#) (Chief Finance Officer)
2. Karl Harder, [Abundance Investment](#) (co-founder of Abundance and Joint Managing Director)
3. Ryan Jude, [Green Finance Institute](#) (Programme Director for Green Taxonomy work)
4. Manuel Nery Nina, [GOPARITY](#), (co-founder)

The speakers presented their experiences with green finance, and specifically with the CMB approach. West-Berkshire spoke to its role as the first UK municipality to successfully implement a CMB. They explained, for example, how investors reside across the whole country, and how diverse activities – like options to donate wildflower seeds to restore local nature – attracted public attention and regard for the CMB approach. As a result, new rooftop solar panels were funded for council-owned sites around West Berkshire.

Abundance partnered with West-Berkshire on this CMB pilot, acting as an investment platform and easily accessible entry point for citizens to invest in clearly defined projects. The Green Finance Institute shared similar insights from its current work on CMBs, and talked about its ongoing campaign to replicate and upscale this approach throughout the country.

Lastly, GOPARITY presented its work as a crowd-lending platform that works with citizen-led initiatives and SMEs in Portugal and Spain. They shared their experiences, reflecting, for example, that raising debt is a taboo for mediterranean municipalities, which made it impossible to directly apply a CMB. Working with Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) and EU programmes on retrofitting were briefly touched upon as well.

A moderated discussion followed these presentations. This discussion put in perspective the role of private savings in energy transition. Most of the money controlled by “heavy players” (like pension funds) ultimately comes from citizens, after all. Investing this money in initiatives like CMBs could be a powerful response to ongoing lobbying for these funds to be invested sustainably.

Some other insights that were highlighted in the discussion include:

- The low risk nature of municipality-based CMBs, as well as high levels of trust in public organisations, are great assets for CMB promotion.
- West Berkshire felt that during COVID-19 lockdowns, community members were paying more attention to social media, where the municipality had advertised the CMB, and that this helped them to succeed.
- BEN referred to the national-level Community Energy Fund as an example to illustrate that innovative and bottom-up financing models are becoming increasingly supported.

- Overall, blended finance between incumbent institutions or municipalities and citizens is seen as a good way forward.
- Local councils are showing stronger ambitions than national governments with respect to net zero goals. As a result, community-based models like CMBs have great future potential.

Day 2

The second day of the event was all about applying the learnings from day 1 to participants' own local contexts, and thinking through how to concretely take action in their own communities. The day opened with a **warm-up exercise** that was done on paper for in-person participants, and using MIRO for online participants. They were asked to brainstorm responses to the following two prompts:

- 1) *Problem Structuring*: What is it that doesn't work in your city's energy transition (projects, policies, initiatives)?
- 2) *Vision*: What change do you want to see to strengthen your city's energy transition?

This warm-up, and in particular responses to the 'visioning' portion, was used as the basis for subsequent sessions throughout the day. To this end, ICLEI took on the task of clustering participants' visions based on common themes.

Figure 3: Impression from first round of the SIE canvas exercise (Bristol)

Before digging deeper into participants' visions, the City Lab method – and its potential to advance local energy transitions – was illustrated via a dialogue session on **“Reflecting EXPERIENCES – how to implement green finance at the local level using a City Lab approach”**.

SONNET partners from BEN, BCC, and SPRU explained that City Labs are experiments in real-world settings that help understand and shape societal transformations. The discussion illustrated how the Lab in Bristol was implemented, and the roles each partner played. Bristol City Council took on scoping, surveying and valuation exercises for CMBs; BEN acted as a trusted intermediary between the local community and the city council; and SPRU has been an academic partner helping to frame the experiment and evaluating the process and outcomes.

Key actions undertaken by the SONNET City Lab in Bristol were highlighted. First, buildings were surveyed to assess the potential for energy saving improvements, to estimate the cost of such work, as well as potential cost savings that could result from improved energy efficiency. Second, a citizen survey was undertaken to better understand how people use the target buildings, how they understand their energy use, and if they might be interested in investing in CMBs as a form of community investment that would provide modest returns.

The hurdles posed by the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and its restrictions were clear. This resulted in clear barriers to reaching out to people and creating trusting and open atmospheres and dialogues. Despite this, however, CMB's potential and high interest among citizens, the council, and BEN was clear!

Next, Session 4, **“THE MICRO LAB – design your own local experiments for energy transition”** took place. ICLEI presented the clusters that they created based on grouping similar responses to the ‘visioning’ warm-up exercise. Participants then voted on which of the nine identified topics they were most interested in diving into deeper, and participants and speakers alike broke into smaller groups to think through how a City Lab could help make their visions a reality.

This exercise was guided by a “City Lab canvas”, designed by ICLEI based on the popular “business model canvas” structure, and was moderated by ICLEI team members. Through both individual brainstorming and group discussion, the breakout groups thought through the following:

- *Needs assessment*: what are the benefits of your idea?
- *Target group*: who are the target groups and stakeholders?
- *Social innovation*: what socially innovative action would your City Lab promote to help reach your vision?
- *Partners*: who could be your main partners, and what other actors are working in your community towards the same goal?
- *Inputs*: what are the main inputs (e.g. funding) needed to develop and implement your idea?
- *Communication channels*: how will you engage your stakeholders?

This exercise resulted in completed canvases, which are included in [Section 2 d\)](#) on outcomes. Each canvas laid out an idea for a potential new City Lab, and multiple participants expressed their eagerness to take these ideas forward.

The final session concluded the event with a **“Panel discussion on motivations, needs and barriers related to financing local energy transitions”**, which revolved around the key question of how to move CMBs forward. The speakers were Richard Lowe from BCC, Rachel Moffat from BEN, and Karl Harder from Abundance.

BCC was optimistic about the future of CMBs, and expressed that political support and administrative checks would need to pass before concrete campaigns could begin. For BEN, the potential of CMBs has been made clear; however, in order to best communicate with the local community, it is important to take a closer look at the co-benefits that can be linked to a CMB, and which respond to specific local concerns. For Abundance, the collaboration between BCC and community organisations is a great partnership to promote CMBs. They emphasised that CMBs should rather be seen as a means to make the implementation of good, bankable projects more feasible.

Fundamentally, CMBs were said to be driven by Bristol City Councils' net zero plans. Peer-learning sessions with other ambitious municipalities, all of whom are piloting CMBs, are being planned to help push this work forward.

2.4 SONNET on Tour in Bristol: outputs

The two outputs from the SONNET on Tour in Bristol event are:

1. The “site visit” [video](#) produced by Bristol City Council (cf. figure 2), which was shown at the event and used subsequently to raise awareness of the CMB method.
2. The City Lab canvases created by participants, included in Appendix 1.

3 ZOOM IN ON SONNET ON TOUR IN WARSAW

3.1 SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: agenda

On 27–28 January 2022, SONNET partners ICLEI Europe, Kozminski University and the City of Warsaw held an online event exploring how social innovation can transform energy systems in Central and Eastern Europe, with a focus on Polish municipalities.

The first part of the event, on 27 January, was an online meeting in English open to all those interested in [social innovation in energy \(SIE\) in Central and Eastern Europe](#). During the event, we talked with the experts and practitioners from the region about the status, characteristics and needs of social innovation in energy in CEE countries, as well as about the role social innovation can play in transforming energy systems in the region. The aim was to raise awareness of SIEs and their transformative potential, and to promote the SIE approach among local energy partners.

Day two of the event, held on 28 January, was a targeted local workshop in Polish for municipalities and local energy actors from across Poland. This workshop zoomed in on the SIE concept, different types of social innovations in energy transitions, and how these can address main energy challenges in Polish cities. Participants had an opportunity to learn more about SIEs, and to dive deeper into the City Lab method. The workshop was planned as an in-person event, but unfortunately had to be held online due to a high number of COVID-19 infections in Poland in January 2022.

Table 3: Agenda of day 1, Thursday, 27 January 2022, open to all

TIME (CET)	PROGRAMME
10:00 – 10:45	<p>ENERGY TALK: Social innovation in energy transitions in Central and Eastern Europe</p> <p>What is the status of social innovations in energy (SIE) in Central and Eastern Europe? What are their characteristics and needs? What helps them develop and thrive?:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Mariya Trifonova, Sofia University- Sabine Hielscher, University of Sussex- Arthur Hinsch, ICLEI- Moderator: Agata Stasik, Kozminski University
10:45 – 11:15	<p>KEYNOTE: How cities can support social innovations in energy – lessons from Warsaw</p>

	<p>How does the City of Warsaw support social innovation in energy transitions? How does the municipality collaborate with diverse energy actors and facilitate the knowledge exchange between them? How does the city want to include SIEs in its future action plans and strategies?:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jacek Kisiel, Deputy Director, Office of Air Protection & Climate Policy, City of Warsaw
11:15 – 11:45	Q&A SESSION: Discuss with the morning's speakers
<i>Coffee break</i>	
12:00 – 12:45	<p>SIEs UNDER A MICROSCOPE</p> <p>Initiatives from across Central and Eastern Europe will present their ideas and actions to make local energy systems greener and more sustainable. They will shed light on the opportunities and challenges facing social innovations in energy in Central and Eastern Europe. What is their potential to transform energy systems in the region? How to enable the development of SIEs? How can we support social innovation and ensure just energy transition for all?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - oPEN Lab in Tartu (Estonia) - ZKlaster in Zgorzelec (Poland)
12:45 – 13:15	<p>LOOKING AHEAD: Takeaways from the discussion</p> <p>Reflection on what has been discussed throughout the day to collaboratively draw key conclusions and takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moderator, Olga Krajewska, ICLEI Europe

Table 4: Agenda of day 2, Friday, 28 January 2022, by-invitation workshop

TIME (CET)	PROGRAMME
10:30 - 11:00	Social Innovation in Energy Transitions Welcome & Get to know each other led by Olga Krajewska, ICLEI Europe.
11:00 – 11:20	Introduction to the social innovation in energy transitions led by Dr Agata Stasik, Kozminski University.

11:20 - 11:50	What are the biggest challenges related to energy transitions in your cities? What are the potential solutions? Group work on MIRO board.
11:50 - 12:30	Discussion in plenary.
12:30 - 13:15	Lunch break
13:15 - 13:35	CITY LAB method Practical introduction to the City Lab method: what is it and how can we use it in the context of energy transitions? led by Marta Strumińska-Kutra, Kozminski University.
13:35 - 13:55	Presentation of Urban Lab in Gdynia led by Joanna Krukowska, the head of Gdynia Urban Lab.
13:55 - 14:10	Presentation of SONNET City Lab in Warsaw led by Bartłomiej Steczowicz from naatu energy, partner of the City Lab.
14:10 - 14:25	Q&A
14:25 - 15:10	Organising City Labs step by step: what should we keep in mind while experimenting with this method? Group work on MIRO board.
15:10 - 15:30	Discussion in plenary
15:30 - 16:00	Presentation of the Green Energy Centre in Warsaw by Jakub Kułach from the Office of Air Protection & Climate Policy, City of Warsaw.

3.2 SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: participants

SONNET successfully met our target of engaging over 30 participants in the event, and increasing the number of SONNET followers in Central and Eastern Europe. Several regional participants had never joined a SONNET event before, and subsequently subscribed to our newsletter and began following our work.

The open online event on 27 January was attended by **34 participants** in total. This is less than we expected considering that 67 people registered, including 18 from Central and Eastern Europe (plus two registrations from Eurasia). To mitigate the lower attendance rate, we integrated the recording of the event in the “[Webinar](#)” section of the SONNET website and published it on our [YouTube playlist](#), as well as disseminating it via SONNET channels.

Figure 4: European countries represented in day one by event registrations

The local workshop on 28 January was attended by **26 people** in total, including representatives of municipalities, research institutes, businesses and NGOs. Most participants (15 people) were from local governments, which indicates that there is great interest in learning more about social

aspects of energy transition among Polish cities. Representatives from **five larger Polish cities** joined the workshop (from Gdynia, Kraków, Poznań, Rzeszów, Toruń, Warsaw), as well as **three municipalities from Poland's coal regions** (Katowice, Konin and Wałbrzych). The other participants (11 people) were from research institutes, including [Kozminski University](#), [KEZO Research Institute](#) and [Institute of Fluid-Flow Machinery at the Polish Academy of Sciences](#); NGOs, including [Institute for Green Future in Konin](#); and businesses, including [naatu energy](#).

Following the conclusion of the local workshop, all attendees were asked to fill in an online evaluation form, which was catered to different types of participants.

This evaluation form demonstrated that the event was a success. Participants were asked to rate their satisfaction with various components of the event on a Likert scale (1= Very Poor; 2= Poor; 3= Okay; 4= Good; 5= Excellent). No one responded below a “3” on any component of the event. Furthermore, participants *on average* rated their satisfaction as follows:

- Satisfaction with the event as a whole: average **4.6**
- Satisfaction with the content of the sessions: average **4.6**
- Satisfaction with the speakers: average **4**
- Satisfaction with interactivity and discussions: average **4**
- Satisfaction with the moderators: average **5**

Participants also had the opportunity to share open-ended reflections via the evaluation form, via email, or in the session itself. This led to the following submissions (translated from Polish):

- **“Thank you for the possibility of attending such an inspiring event”**
- **“I will gladly participate in the next meetings organised by the SONNET partners. The workshop was very interesting and showed a lot of ideas that can be adopted in our city.”**

This workshop made clear the great big need to continue dialogue on energy transition in Poland with cities and other local energy actors. Given this, Dr. Agata Stasik from Kozminski University offered to organise regular online meetings for interested participants. **This is an impressive outcome that will outlive even the SONNET project!**

Dr. Stasik prepared a survey to determine 1) how many people are interested in such an initiative and, 2) what topics are most interesting for participants. The proposed topics include (but are not limited to): decarbonisation of the heating system; energy cooperatives after transposition of RED II; calculation and modelling of emissions in cities; green municipal bonds and other innovative financing mechanisms; and engagement of citizens in energy transition. Each meeting will be attended by municipalities, think-tanks, NGOs, energy companies, and others, who will present on a selected topic.

The first meeting was scheduled for 23 March 2022 and was dedicated to discussing strategies for decarbonising heating sectors in Polish cities. More information about the meetings can be found [here](#) on Kozminski University's website.

3.3 SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: minutes

Day 1

The online event began with a brief welcome and introduction to the SONNET project, followed by an opening **Energy Talk** with four experts, who discussed the main challenges facing energy transition in Central and Eastern Europe, and how SIE can help address them. More specifically, the panel consisted of: Sabine Hielscher, Sussex University, the UK; Mariya Trifnova, Sofia University, Bulgaria; Arthur Hinsch, ICLEI Europe, Germany; and Agata Stasik, Kozminski University, Poland.

After a brief introduction to social innovations in energy (SIE) and SONNET's SIE typology, the panellists zoomed in on the characteristics of energy systems in CEE countries and what impact these have on SIEs. They pointed to hindering factors, like coal dependency, top-down governance, few energy players dominating energy systems, lack of funds and lower salaries, high energy poverty rates, and a lack of awareness and education regarding climate change. However, the discussion was not all about challenges. Panellists emphasised that these very challenges might also create space for innovation, new solutions and partnerships.

Of note, to be able to implement some types of SIEs, like energy cooperatives, it is essential to have clear and supportive regulations, as well as entities coordinating the process. The Energy Talk ended with an important point from Sabine Hielscher that it is not only regulation that must change, but also the culture of how people think and organise energy. This shift will lead to greater citizen engagement for energy transition and more openness towards SIEs.

Other insights that emerged in the discussion include:

- We are currently facing a dynamic situation in energy markets: new political frameworks at the EU level (European Green Deal, Fit for 55), risks and political tensions around fossil fuel phase-out, rising gas prices, etc.
- Social innovation is strongly tied to legislation and legal frameworks on all governance levels: European, national and local. How certain SIEs will work in practice (e.g. energy cooperatives) will depend on how policies are transposed into concrete national energy laws.
- To raise awareness about energy transition, it is important to talk not only about climate and environmental benefits, but also about social and economic impacts – these are more relatable to people.
- Coordinating organisations that push for energy transition are important, no matter who they are. This role can be played even by churches and religious assemblies.

The Energy Talk was followed by a **keynote speech** on how cities can support SIEs, and lessons learnt from Warsaw. The keynote was delivered by Jacek Kisiel, Deputy Director at the Office of Air Protection & Climate Policy in the City of Warsaw. He emphasised the crucial role local governments must play to reach ambitious climate goals, and presented Warsaw's action plan towards decarbonisation. He dove deeper into socially innovative actions that either have been carried out in Warsaw, or will be implemented in the future. This included:

- *Warsaw Climate Panel*, citizen assembly developing set of recommendations for the municipality
- *Green Energy Centre*, municipal energy advisory system for individual and institutional investor
- *Zlikwiduj kopciucha*, anti-smog campaign
- *Zero-energy district in Jazdow*.

The last session of Day 1 put **SIEs UNDER A MICROSCOPE**, exploring two SIE initiatives from the CEE region: [oPEN Lab](#) (Tartu, Estonia) and [ZKlaster](#) (Zgorzelec, Poland).

Merit Tatar from the Institute of Baltic Studies presented the oPEN Lab project, a 5-year Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation project with an impressive 20 million EUR budget. oPEN Lab aims to create urban living labs in three European cities (including Tartu) to test energy positive neighbourhoods. Social innovation is a crucial component of the project, which makes use of co-design and collaboration with residents and stakeholders.

The City Lab experiment in Tartu will be carried out in the Annelinna district, which is a challenging neighbourhood, both with respect to its Soviet-era urban planning and architecture (big apartment complexes, limited space), as well as social challenges (dense population, vulnerable groups). Merit Tatar emphasised the importance of using tailored communication with citizens. She recommended not only focusing on climate and environmental benefits, but also on social and economic benefits, like health or cheaper electricity bills.

Figure 5: Screenshots from OpenLap (Tartu, Estonia) presentation

Agnieszka Spirydowicz, the president of ZKlaster, explained what an energy cluster is, the types of engaged partners, and how such a cluster works in practice. She shed light on challenges that hinder the deployment of renewable energy in the Zgorzelec region, like dependency on coal, low climate awareness among citizens, and distrust in new energy solutions. She explained that the goals of ZKlaster are to build an independent local energy market based on renewable energy sources as well as to rebrand the region from a coal dependent one, to a one open for green investments. ZKlaster contributes to a just transition in the region.

Figure 6: Screenshot from Z-Klaster (Poland) presentation

Day 2

The second day of the *SONNET on Tour in Warsaw* event was a practical workshop for Polish municipalities and other local energy actors, held in the local language. The event was divided into two main thematic blocks: the first was dedicated to social innovation in energy transitions, and the second one was focused on the City Lab method as an example of SIE.

The day opened with a **welcome** and get to know each other round that included a short presentation of the SONNET project. Participants introduced themselves, sharing:

Figure 7: Impression from first round of the SIE canvas exercise (Warsaw)

- Who are you and what do you do?
- What made you take part in our workshop?
- What is the project you are most proud of?

Dr. Agata Stasik from Kozminski University **introduced the topic of social innovation in energy transitions**. She explained the concept and different types of SIEs, using the SONNET typology. She then zoomed in on the local context in Poland and clarified why now is a good time to start experimenting with SIEs.

After the introduction to SIEs, all participants split into **four facilitated groups** and discussed the **main challenges of energy transition in their cities**. They brainstormed what works and what doesn't with respect to local energy transition, and what can be done better. This exercise was organised using a MIRO board.

The biggest challenges of energy transition indicated by the participants were:

- Coal boilers phase-out
- Lack of vision for energy transition in Poland
- Lack of collaboration between neighbouring municipalities for energy transition
- Low awareness regarding climate change and environmental protection; wrong energy habits

During the group work, participants also brainstormed potential solutions that could support and accelerate the energy transition in their cities. They came up with the following propositions:

- to create a special unit dedicated to energy transition in every municipality acting as an advisory board;
- to finalise an intermunicipal agreement on the joint purchase of energy;
- to create new business models and mechanisms for financing energy transition; and
- to develop better monitoring systems for energy efficiency in buildings.

Group facilitators presented all ideas in a plenary session, during which time participants could continue the discussion as a group.

After the lunch break, Dr. Marta Strumińska-Kutra from Kozminski University led a practical presentation to **introduce the City Lab method**. She explained the method, and presented six examples of City Labs created as part of SONNET.

This was followed by a closer examination of two City Labs in Poland. The first, [UrbanLab in Gdynia](#), was presented by Joanna Krukowska. This was a 3-year project (2019-2021) financed by the Polish Ministry of Funds and Regional Policy, which focused on three topics: citizen participation, adaptation to climate change, and adaptation to life in- and post-pandemic. The Lab tested many interesting solutions, such as [online dialogue platform](#), Urban Cafe, and micro innovations.

UrbanLab Gdynia to program służący do dzielenia się wiedzą. To przestrzeń dialogu pomiędzy mieszkańcami miasta, organizacjami pozarządowymi i instytucjami miejskimi, w tym środowiskiem naukowym i biznesowym. Każdy z międzysektorowych i interdyscyplinarnych komponentów UrbanLabu polega na diagnozowaniu wyzwań i potrzeb oraz poszukiwaniu innowacyjnych rozwiązań, które pogłębią lepsze rozumienie problemów i zbliżą nas do adaptacji, łagodzenia lub przeciwdziałania trwającym i nadchodzącym kryzysom.

Figure 8: Screenshots from presentation of the UrbanLab (Gdynia, Poland)

The second Lab was the Warsaw City Lab organised as a part of the SONNET project, presented by Bartłomiej Steczowicz from naatu energy. The goal of the Lab was to change energy behaviour in 11 households in Warsaw. To do so, energy use in these households was measured and shared with the participants, alongside guidance indicating what could be done better to save energy. The City of Warsaw expressed interest in scaling-up this experiment in the future, bringing it to more households.

Cele City Labu

wykreowanie innowacji społecznych w sektorze efektywności energetycznej poprzez poszukiwanie sposobów na zmniejszenie zużycia energii w codziennym życiu

benefity dla mieszkańców (oświetlenie premium, mniejsze zużycie, niższe rachunki, świadomość zużycia)

skalowanie wypracowanych rozwiązań poprzez wykorzystanie ich w zasobie mieszkaniowym miasta

Figure 9: Screenshot from SONNET City Lab in Warsaw presentation

The final round of group work guided participants to invent their own City Labs. Each Lab contributed to the following four climate goals, which were mapped during the morning group exercise:

- Zero-emission heating in the city
- Reducing energy use in buildings

- Energy and climate education & raising awareness
- Citizen participation for energy transition

This was guided by the “City Lab Canvas” model, adapted by the SONNET project for this purpose. The resulting canvases are available to view in [Appendix 2](#).

The final agenda point was to learn more about Warsaw’s Green Energy Centre, which is a group of four energy consultants advising citizens on energy issues, such as installation of solar panels and exchange of old coal boilers. The initiative was presented by Jakub Kułach from the Office of Air Protection & Climate Policy, City of Warsaw.

The overall conclusion of the workshop was that now is a good moment to implement SIEs in Poland. Rising energy prices, combined with ambitious climate and energy goals at the EU level, open a window of opportunity for SIEs in the country. Although regulatory and price uncertainty makes it difficult to plan actions, the old energy system in Poland is in a moment of transition, creating space to look for new solutions. Furthermore, this comes at a time when a lot of European funding is becoming available to help achieve climate goals and just transition.

3.4 SONNET on Tour in Warsaw: outputs

The two main outputs from the SONNET on Tour event in Warsaw are:

- The creation of a new group of Polish energy actors, who will meet regularly online to discuss energy transition (the first meeting took place on 23 March 2022 and zoomed in on strategies for decarbonization the heating sector in cities, see [here](#) for information and contacts at Kozminski University)
- The design of a number of new City Labs, using the City Lab Canvas (see Appendix 2).

Exercise 2: Challenges & Solutions: Thematic clusters

2

This is to match you into the right group of people, who have a similar vision / idea - this way, we hope for you to have the most engaging exchange.

Which box do you fit in with your topic? Drag you card (with name) to the according box

IDEA / TOPIC / GROUP 1	IDEA / TOPIC / GROUP 2	IDEA / TOPIC / GROUP 3
<p>Equity, justice, inequality</p> <p>Addressing issues such as people not being able to afford energy, not being able to get a supplier generally accustomed for households around energy (Sabine)</p> <p>Home owners or renters in bad poverty unable to invest in energy improvements GS</p> <p>Districts with high energy poverty (Olga)</p> <p>Energy efficient homes being too expensive and out-pricing people (gentrification)</p> <p>Allowing all citizen to be prosumers not just the ones who can afford it (Sabine)</p> <p>inequalities - and other priorities</p> <p>Funding to ensure that affordable and social housing is energy efficient without increasing rent to the point of driving locals out</p>	<p>Government regulations not supportive enough</p> <p>Easier access to renewables, like solar panels (Olga)</p> <p>Lack of central gov't support / regulation / funding requiring action</p> <p>Making it easier for community energy initiatives to realise the work (Sabine)</p>	<p>Need new regulations on buildings</p> <p>Home owners with disposable income do not prioritise energy improvements GS</p> <p>Standard of housing very poor; lack of money and to some extent lack of easy solutions (dominated by stone houses which are difficult to retrofit)</p> <p>Solar panels only for private houses; no initiatives to install solar panels on communal buildings (Olga)</p> <p>charges to the building trade to improve retrofit understanding and skills</p> <p>Mandates on retrofit with public funding support for those financially at risk GS</p>
<p>Idea / Topic / Group 4</p> <p>Need new funding models</p> <p>Funding needs: research, innovation instead of trial and error technology GS</p> <p>Funding models still tend to be based on R&D without including wider benefits GS</p> <p>Innovative models for people being able to finance and carry out energy efficiency measures in their homes with some support from the council and national government (Sabine)</p> <p>Blended private and public sector funding GS</p> <p>more recognition of community action and better funding to enable this</p> <p>Funding to set up retrofit programmes however unlikely to have return that would justify bond issue</p>	<p>Idea / Topic / Group 5</p> <p>Need better policy to decarbonise mobility</p> <p>Making it less dangerous to cycle around the city (Sabine)</p> <p>No EVs infrastructure (Olga)</p> <p>Mobility policy not moving forward to restrict car use in city center (Niklas)</p> <p>Transport very challenging as area is semi rural, so difficult to provide sufficient links to compete with cars</p> <p>better integrated transport provision around the city as well as into / out of the centre</p> <p>Do an experiment with a car free city centre (at least that) (Niklas)</p> <p>Better infrastructure for bikes and better public transport (Olga)</p> <p>Better public transport and less private cars in the city. More and better cycling routes (Sabine)</p> <p>Anything which could reduce car usage would provide significant improvement as physical environment very unsuited to dense car ownership</p> <p>Love to fund trial with on call shuttle buses</p>	<p>Idea / Topic / Group 6</p> <p>Need more meaningful partnership with locals</p> <p>political mistrust - across party allegiances</p> <p>the style of projects varies across villages with some reluctance of local villages GS</p> <p>Including a broad range of citizens in energy projects - issues of inclusion (Sabine)</p> <p>Greater partnership working with community and private sector themes GS</p> <p>More inclusion of community issues and greater possibilities for energy initiative to get involved in offshore wind developments (Sabine)</p> <p>recognition of the huge need to engage everyone in the energy transition and varied ways of spreading the message across the different segments of the population</p>
<p>Idea / Topic / Group 7</p> <p>Need more integrated solutions</p> <p>For existing initiatives to work across food, energy, etc. issues a bit more (Sabine)</p> <p>Integrated solutions across sectors</p>	<p>Idea / Topic / Group 8</p> <p>Need better outreach/education</p> <p>More energy education, small community engagement in local energy projects (Olga)</p> <p>regeneration of the new skills needed and better provision of upskilling across the city so that everyone can access necessary</p> <p>Easy accessible knowledge through an energy advisor supporting citizens</p> <p>Better energy education (Olga)</p>	<p>Idea / Topic / Group 9</p> <p>Need more decentralised power to local level</p> <p>insufficient local powers to mandate change GS</p> <p>No support for energy communities (Olga)</p> <p>More power on the local level - city level (Olga)</p>

Exercise 3: City Lab canvas

TOPIC 1 (in-person breakout group): Accountability/governance to achieve energy transition

Accountability / Governance to achieve energy transition.

Group 1 (in person)

How to (not) do this: Just note down bullet points of your discussion and the ideas that you seem to like best - the canvas should help you to get a deeper insight, AND NOT get you stuck with perfectionism.

<p>Needs Assessment What are the benefits of your idea?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To create shared ownership/accountability. - Makes climate change more relatable/achievable action. 	<p>Target Group Who are the target groups and stakeholders (also sectors or policy areas)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Everyone! - Assess existing structures to understand. - Focus on biggest inputters whilst not leaving anyone behind 	<p>Social Innovation / Actions What is the Social Innovation, i.e. the Action or Product, that your City Lab promotes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct line between measures and accountability. - Shared tracker - Managed One City Board.
<p>Partners Who are your main partners / actors working for the same cause?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One City Boards or equivalent - Research institute 	<p>Input Factors What are the main input factors to develop and implement your idea?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Measurement framework (Solar green city tracker) - Coordination / management - Independent assessment/verification ↑ Research Institute - Auditing costs ££ - shouldn't be a barrier to action. - Financial incentives - General incentives - LA regulations. 	<p>Communication Channels How will you engage your stakeholders?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Officers setting plans built in to service plans. - Influencing groups reports

Risks

- Reputational.
- Politicians not re-elected
- Lack of consequence for inaction.

TOPIC 2: Equitable energy solutions

Group 2 equitable energy solutions

<p>Needs Assessment What are the benefits of your idea?</p> <p>[Redacted]</p> <p>Making new technologies affordable</p> <p>energy coop model: each shareholder has 1 vote, no matter how much shares they have</p>	<p>Target Group Who are the target groups and stakeholders (also sectors or policy areas)?</p> <p>[Redacted]</p> <p>wider range of people - also less wealthy ones</p>	<p>Social Innovation / Actions What is the Social Innovation, i.e. the Action or Product, that your City Lab promotes?</p> <p>[Redacted]</p> <p>making time for people - universal basic income or maximum working week</p>
<p>Partners Who are your main partners / actors working for the same cause?</p> <p>[Redacted]</p> <p>Pilots in Barcelona (basic income) - to learn from</p>	<p>Input Factors What are the main input factors to develop and implement your idea?</p> <p>[Redacted]</p>	<p>Communication Channels How will you engage your stakeholders?</p> <p>[Redacted]</p>

TOPIC 3: New funding models

TOPIC 4: Affordable and energy efficient homes

5 APPENDIX 2: CITY LAB CANVASES FROM WARSAW

Exercise 1: Challenges & Solutions for energy transition in your city

ĆWICZENIE 1: Wyzwania transformacji energetycznej w Twoim mieście

Wskazówka: jakie wyzwanie przychodzi Ci na myśl? Co stanowi Was do udziału w warstwie i o czym chętniejście rozmawialiście podczas spotkania z innymi? Tematów jest bardzo wiele, np. transport, wykorzystanie odnawialnych źródeł energii, zaangażowanie społeczne, ubóstwo energetyczne, energooszczędność, nieistniejąca cena energii, edukacja itd.

Analiza Problemów: jakie są największe wyzwania transformacji energetycznej w Twoim mieście? Jakimi działaniami możesz je rozwiązać? Jakie działania nie przyniosą oczekiwanych efektów?

Miejsce: jakie są rozwiązania? Co należy zmienić, aby przyspieszył transformacja energetyczna w Twoim mieście?

Exercise 2: Challenges & Solutions: Thematic clusters

- Decarbonising heating
- Reducing energy consumption
- Education for energy
- Citizen engagement in energy transition

WYZWANIA W CIEPŁOWNICTWIE / GRUPA 1

OBNIŻENIE ZUŻYCIA ENERGII I EFEKTYWNOŚĆ ENERGETYCZNA BUDYNKÓW / GRUPA 2

EDUKACJA o ENERGETYCE / GRUPA 3

UCZESTNICTWO MIESZKAŃCÓW / GRUPA 4

POMYSŁ / TEMAT / GRUPA 5

POMYSŁ / TEMAT / GRUPA 6

Exercise 3: City Lab canvas

TOPIC 1: Decarbonising heating

ĆWICZENIE 2: Tworzenie City Labu

GRUPA 1: Zeroemisyjne ciepłownictwo w mieście

TOPIC 2: Reducing energy consumption

GRUPA 2: Obniżanie zużycia energii - efektywność energetyczna

<p>Ocena potrzeb Na jaką potrzebę chcemy odpowiedzieć?</p> <p>czego najbardziej potrzebują miasta? jakiego wsparcia?</p>	<p>Grupa docelowa Kto są grupy docelowe i interesariusze (również sektory lub obszary polityki)?</p>	<p>Innowacje społeczne / Działania Czy jest innowacja społeczna, czyli działanie lub produkt, który Wasz City Lab testuje?</p> <p>atrakcyjny produkt dla miasta i mieszkańców; śledzenie zużycia energii na rzecz efektywności</p> <p>analiza tego, co można zrobić: w celu dekarbonizacji/efektowności na poziomie małego miasta, odrębny</p> <p>otwartość na innowacje (w miastach)</p>
<p>Partnerzy Kim są Wasi główni partnerzy / aktorzy działający na rzecz tej samej sprawy?</p> <p>partnerstwo miasto-przedsiębiorcy</p> <p>granka 120 tys. zł związana z budownictwem pAKAZ</p> <p>oddany dla projektu partner po stronie miasta (dedykowana jednostka) - ważne dla innych partnerów - miasto jako lider</p>	<p>Nakłady Co jest niezbędne aby rozwinąć i wdrożyć Wasz pomysł? (To mogą być nakłady finansowe, ale również trening personelu, system monitorowania rezultatów, itd.)</p> <p>ryzyka związane z zewnętrznymi/unijny m finansowaniem: dużo czasu, a sytuacja dynamiczna</p> <p>granty miasta-firmy</p> <p>innowacyjne finansowanie: Zielone Obligacje? Zielone Fundusze? (taksonomia)</p>	<p>Kanały komunikacyjne W jaki sposób zaangażujecie Waszych interesariuszy?</p>

TOPIC 3: Education for energy

GRUPA 3: Edukacja, podnoszenie świadomości - mieszkańcy i interesariusze: kwestie energii i klimatu

TOPIC 4: Citizen engagement in energy transition

6 APPENDIX 2: EC SUMMARY REQUIREMENTS

Changes with respect to the DoA

The submission date of the deliverable has been changed from the end of August 2021 to end of March 2022 due to COVID 19 restrictions that had an impact on the feasibility of implementing workshops and events, as well as the ability to travel throughout 2021, to increase chances for in-person implementation of the workshops. Further, also the finalisation of the SONNET City Labs had been delayed due to COVID 19 restrictions to the effect of shifting the regional workshops to the end of the local activities as well.

These changes were agreed by the project officer. There are no other changes in scope and content of the deliverable.

Dissemination and uptake

In combination with the SONNET City Lab guide (D4.8, [Dembek et al. 2022](#)) this deliverable informs about the achievements of the SONNET City Labs and the learnings they created. This deliverable will be uploaded and publicly accessible on the SONNET website.

Short Summary of results

In reference to the SONNET objectives, this report captures the contributions of the SONNET on Tour workshops to accelerate sustainable energy transitions for those involved in social innovation in energy from policy makers to academics, students, and citizens.

This deliverable includes: 1) an introduction to the original ambition and the ways it was implemented under COVID 19 restrictions and 2) an overview of the agenda, participants, meeting minutes and outputs for both workshops carried out. In the appendix a more detailed documentation of the outputs can be found.

Evidence of accomplishment

This deliverable.

